

HAYDARKOL ZOOSPHERE AND THEIR ECOLOGY

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Annotation. *In this article, based on the needs of the times, environmental information about the problems of industrial ecology and environmental pollution in our society is highlighted by giving examples.*

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One can talk about the Haydarkol zoosphere and its ecology for hours. Conditions for ecological development of sustainable industry creation and preservation of various levels of experts, including nature Managers can help people, they are at different levels development, existence, functioning of ecosystems and the biosphere as a whole they have deep knowledge about its laws.

In fact, industrial ecology is living in different parts of the biosphere and as interaction complexes of non-living components the laws of development and existence of biogeocenoses, organisms and is a science that studies the interaction of their living environment. Historically, the term "ecology" is derived from two Greek words "oikos" - house, abode, abode, and 'logos' is literally 'living organisms and their on relations between the environment" means.

This term was introduced to science by the German biologist Ernst Heikel in 1866 biology that studies the interaction of organisms with the environment introduced science. In the 2nd volume of the book "General Morphology of Organisms" E. Haeckel gave the following definition of ecology as a science: "Ecology means we general about the interaction of organisms with the environment we understand the concept here in a broad sense to all circumstances we will appeal," he said.

Currently, industrial ecology is usually a person's "own home" - the biosphere, its characteristics, interaction with man and the whole human society and is called the science of interaction.

Indeed, industrial ecology is not only a science, but also for all mankind became and continues to be a way of thinking and behaving. Industrial ecology is humane from a

civilizational point of view, including spirituality, understanding of the unity of man and nature, high culture became one of the parties. The nature that surrounds us is the life of all mankind is a source of resources for its economy, but unfortunately Science is the problem of the influence of civilization on nature for a long time moved away. If we consider the successive stages of the development of industrial ecology if we observe, then at first it was two specific parts of botany and zoology.

In the middle of the 20th century, ecology significantly expanded its scope and supraorganismic systems, which are a collection of organisms together with the environment has become a branch of biology, and they call it general ecology was named. Currently, industrial ecology has an interdisciplinary meaning, became general ecology.

Based on the experience of environmental protection analysis, ecology as a science should be a synthesis of scientific disciplines - biology, geology, physics, chemistry, economics, etc. Environmental problems requires broad philosophical understanding, creation of new aesthetic concepts. In ecology, the most complex scientific constructions are combined with practical problemsrequires immediate resolution.

In this regard, the main tasks of industrial ecology are:

- The functioning and development of the biosphere as an integral system
- understand the laws;
- Natural and anthropogenic origin of environmental components
- to study the reaction to the disturbance of influence;
- The impact of human civilization on the environment is allowed
- determine the boundaries;
- Influence on the environment, its existence and development ways of developing society that guarantee compliance with its limits development of conceptual ideas and recommendations.

So the above tasks confirm that ecology is just is not a scientific discipline, but a problem-oriented system of scientific knowledge. In conclusion, it should be said that environmental pollution is common negative of non-physical, chemical, biological or information agencies is a new entry or emergence that leads to consequences.

Natural environmental pollution as a result of the influence of natural factors and human economic 81 may appear as a result of the activity. Natural pollution natural disasters occurs as a result of (volcanic eruptions, hurricanes, floods) Industrial ecology is a holistic science that depends not only on physical and biological phenomena, it is natural and serves as a unique

bridge between social sciences. It is linear is not a structured science, that is, it does not develop vertically - from simple to complex - it develops horizontally and is different covers a wide range of issues in the fields.

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